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Sperm Kinetics in Boars Assessed by CASA: Influence of Biological and Technical Factors

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Introduction

Artificial insemination is an essential tool in modern pig production, and its effectiveness largely depends on proper semen quality assessment. In many insemination centers, sperm motility is still subjectively estimated under the microscope, which may generate operator variability and errors in semen evaluation. CASA systems allow objective and repeatable analysis of sperm motility and kinetics; however, their results may be influenced by technical and biological factors that must be standardized. Among these, warming time prior to analysis, breed, and different management factors are particularly relevant. Understanding their effect under practical conditions is key to optimizing semen quality control.

The objective of this study was to evaluate the influence of breed and warming time on sperm kinetic parameters measured by CASA, as well as to analyze additional biological and management factors in Duroc boars.

Materials and Methods

The study was conducted in an artificial insemination center under routine working conditions. A total of 3,300 measurements were performed using ejaculates from Duroc, Landrace, and Pietrain boars. Samples were diluted according to the center's standard protocols and analyzed using a CASA system. For each ejaculate, motility and kinetic parameters were measured at different warming times prior to analysis, ranging from 0

to 50 minutes, with measurements taken every 5 minutes.

Nine kinetic parameters were recorded: total motility (MotTot), progressive motility (MotProg), curvilinear velocity (VCL), straight-line velocity (VSL), average path velocity (VAP), linearity (LIN), straightness (STR), amplitude of lateral head displacement (ALH), and beat cross frequency (BCF). Spermatozoa were considered progressive when $STR \geq 75\%$ and static when $VCL < 10 \mu\text{m/s}$.

In Duroc boars, a sub-analysis was additionally performed to evaluate the effect of genetic line, semen collection frequency, farm of origin, and age. Data were analyzed using mixed repeated-measures models to assess the effects of breed, warming time, and their interactions, as well as the influence of additional factors in Duroc.

Results and Discussion

Breed and warming time prior to analysis significantly influenced the sperm kinetic parameters evaluated by CASA, demonstrating the combined influence of biological and technical factors in semen quality assessment. Among the breeds studied, Landrace boars showed higher total and progressive motility values and higher parameters associated with more efficient and directional movement, such as STR and LIN, compared with Duroc and Pietrain. These results indicate breed-related differences in sperm movement patterns and suggest a greater functional potential of Landrace semen under the analytical conditions used.

Warming time had a progressive effect on sperm kinetics. As exposure to analysis temperature increased, significant modifications were observed in parameters such as VCL, ALH, and BCF, reflecting a

gradual deterioration of flagellar beating and lateral head displacement amplitude. At the same time, directionality indices tended to increase, probably as a consequence of reduced lateral movement amplitude. This suggests that some changes detected by CASA may be attributable to thermal variations. The presence of breed × time interactions in several parameters indicates that the kinetic response to warming is not homogeneous among breeds.

In the sub-analysis conducted in Duroc boars, semen collection frequency significantly influenced sperm velocities, particularly VCL and VAP, suggesting a relationship between reproductive management and semen motility. Furthermore, the genetic line × time interaction observed in VCL demonstrates intra-breed variability in thermal sensitivity of sperm movement.

Conclusions

Breed and warming time prior to analysis decisively affect sperm kinetic parameters obtained through CASA. Landrace boars showed higher progressive motility and movement efficiency, whereas prolonged warming significantly altered several velocity and kinetic pattern parameters. In Duroc, higher semen collection frequency was associated with higher velocities, and genetic line modulated the response to warming. A standardized warming period of 15–20 minutes allows minimization of technical variation and yields more consistent and comparable results. Standardization of protocols integrating biological and management variability is essential to improve the accuracy of semen quality control in commercial pig artificial insemination centers.

References

1. Postigo Arribas E. (2025). *Análisis multifactorial de la motilidad espermática en porcino para la mejora del control de calidad seminal*. Master's Thesis, Complutense University of Madrid.

Oxidation-Reduction Potential as an Indicator of Semen Quality

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Introduction

Oxidation-reduction potential (ORP) has been proposed as an indicator of boar semen quality during storage. ORP reflects the balance between oxidizing and reducing agents. Because porcine semen contains a high proportion of polyunsaturated fatty acids, sperm cells are especially vulnerable to oxidative stress, which can impair motility, acrosome integrity, DNA stability, and overall fertilizing capacity.

Materials and Methods

The study evaluated ejaculates from 10 boars collected at the same artificial insemination center. Semen doses (60 mL) were prepared using two different extenders, M and K, and ORP was measured at 0, 24, 48, and 72 hours after dilution.

Results

The results showed significant differences ($p < 0.001$) between the two extenders at all time points. Semen preserved with extender M consistently exhibited lower ORP values than semen stored with extender K, indicating a more favorable redox balance and better preservation conditions.

ORP remained relatively stable over time in both groups, although values were consistently higher in group K.

Conclusions

The authors conclude that ORP could be a useful routine marker in semen collection centers to assess semen preservation quality under different storage conditions. Increased oxidation during storage appears to be associated with a progressive decline in sperm quality, particularly in terms of motility and acrosome integrity.

Bibliographic References

1. Menegat, M. B., Mellagi, A. P. G., Bortolin, R. C., Menezes, T. A., Vargas, A. R., Bernardi, M. L., Wentz, I., Gelain, D. P., Moreira, J. C. F., & Bortolozzo, F. P. (2017). Sperm quality and oxidative status as affected by homogenization of liquid-stored boar semen diluted in short- and long-term extenders. *Animal Reproduction Science*, 179, 67–79. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anireprosci.2017.02.003>
2. Khoi, H. X., Shimizu, K., Yoneda, Y., Minagawa, I., Abe, Y., Kuwabara, Y., Sasanami, T., & Kohsaka, T. (2021). Monitoring the reactive oxygen species in spermatozoa during liquid storage of boar semen and its correlation with sperm motility, free thiol content and seasonality. *Andrologia*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/and.14237>
3. Li, J.; Zhao, W.; Zhu, J.; Ju, H.; Liang, M.; Wang, S.; Chen, S.; Ferreira-Dias, G.; Liu, Z. Antioxidants and Oxidants in Boar Spermatozoa and Their Surrounding Environment Are Associated with AMPK Activation during Liquid Storage. *Vet. Sci.* 2023, 10, 214. <https://doi.org/10.3390/vetsci10030214>

Sow death risk factor analysis based on production data of 16 farms

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Introduction

Sow mortality has risen in recent years, creating major challenges for animal welfare, farm productivity, and economic sustainability. Previous studies highlight influences such as parity, season, and farrowing-related complications, yet limited evidence exists for mortality patterns across reproductive stages in Spanish sow herds. This study aimed to characterize stage-specific mortality and identify key risk factors at herd and sow levels.

Methods

Individual sow records from January 2019 to December 2024 were collected from 16 Spanish farms. Incidence rates were estimated using two-level Poisson regression models with an offset, applied separately to two risk periods: insemination to farrowing and farrowing to the next insemination. Herd-level variables, including the gilt replacement strategy, were modelled as fixed effects. Pearson's correlations were used to assess associations between herd-level mortality and indicators such as herd size and pigs weaned per sow per year (PWSY). At the parity level, univariate models were run with sow-level covariates. Additionally, three matched case-control studies compared reproductive and lifetime performance between deceased sows and matched controls.

Results

Annual mortality rose from 5.2% to 9.7% during 2019 to 2024. Across the 16 farms, 55.59% of sow deaths occurred before farrowing and 44.41% after. Mortality peaked during late gestation (days 105–118) and during the first- and fourth-weeks post-farrowing. Among farm-level factors, internal gilt replacement was associated with post-farrowing mortality. At the sow level, service frequency and parity played important roles. Before farrowing, sows with parity ≥ 3 and those that received only a single service exhibited a higher mortality incidence. After farrowing, increased mortality was observed in parity 1 sows and those with repeat breeding. Seasonal effects were evident, with the highest mortality rates found in sows bred in spring and farrowing in summer. Matched case-control analysis revealed that parity 0 sows had a younger age at first service, and deceased sows had shorter gestational length, fewer piglets born, born alive, and a higher incidence of stillbirth fetuses at their last litter. Comparing the lifetime performance, dead sows had younger gilt age at first service, fewer parity at removal, higher average number of piglets born, born alive, born still and born mummified per parity, but they had fewer weaned piglets and nonproductive days.

Discussion

Mortality was concentrated around late gestation and the post-farrowing period, identifying these as critical high-risk stages. Peaks occurred shortly before farrowing and during the first weeks after, indicating the need for closer monitoring and potentially earlier movement to farrowing facilities. A secondary rise in mortality after four weeks post-farrowing appeared linked not to weaning itself, but to a vulnerable subset of sows with reproductive or health issues that remained in the herd.

Cause-of-death data were limited, with “sudden death” dominating due to lack of post-mortem confirmation. Misclassification is likely, particularly between dystocia-related deaths and sudden death. Prolapse emerged as the most reliably identified cause, while other categories lacked diagnostic precision. This highlights the need for improved on-farm recording and training.

Multiple biological and management factors contributed to mortality risk. Peripartum deaths are associated with cardiovascular failure, infections, and prolapse¹, exacerbated by stressors such as heat, body weight, and social interactions². Seasonal patterns showed higher mortality in summer, likely driven by heat stress, particularly during recent extreme heat waves in Spain. Infectious factors such as PRRSV may also play a role, especially given associations with stillbirths and seasonal patterns favouring viral persistence³.

Parity influenced mortality nonlinearly, with higher risk in parity 1 and ≥ 6 sows. Reproductive history mattered: repeat-service sows showed lower gestation mortality but higher post-farrowing mortality, suggesting underlying health vulnerabilities. Herd-level effects indicated that internal gilt replacement systems may increase risk if gilt development is poorly managed. Dead sows showed higher stillbirth and mummification rates and fewer weaned piglets, suggesting these reproductive indicators may serve as early warning signs of mortality. Overall, improving monitoring, environmental management, gilt development, and data quality is essential to reduce mortality and enhance herd sustainability.

Conclusions

Late gestation and early postpartum represent the most critical windows for sow survival.

Internal gilt replacement, repeat breeding, and vulnerability of parity 1 sows emerged as important risk factors. Seasonal patterns indicate a need for environmental mitigation during summer farrowing. Performance patterns of deceased sows support incorporating early reproductive signals into long-term management and culling decisions.

Reference

1. Monteiro MS, Matias DN, Poor AP, et al. Causes of Sow Mortality and Risks to Post-Mortem Findings in a Brazilian Intensive Swine Production System. *Animals*. 2022;12(14):14. doi:10.3390/ani12141804
2. Iida R, Koketsu Y. Climatic factors associated with peripartum pig deaths during hot and humid or cold seasons. *Preventive Veterinary Medicine*. 2014;115(3):166-172. doi:10.1016/j.prevetmed.2014.03.019
3. Lugo Mesa V, Quinonez Munoz A, Sobhy NM, Corzo CA, Goyal SM. Survival of Porcine Reproductive and Respiratory Syndrome Virus (PRRSV) in the Environment. *Veterinary Sciences*. 2024;11(1):22. doi:10.3390/vetsci11010022

Hot or cold? The effect of temperature on sow mortality

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Introduction

Heat stress has become an increasingly important welfare and productivity challenge in swine production. In recent years, Europe has experienced record-breaking summer heat waves, raising concerns about climate-related impacts on sow survival. Sixteen Spanish farms reported noticeable summer peaks in sow mortality, with a marked upward trend after 2022. This study aims to estimate the fraction of deaths attributable to non-optimal temperatures on sow mortality.

Method

Daily temperature fields with municipality-level data to derive the daily average temperature and humidity were used to reconstruct local climatic exposures from 2019–2024. Entry and removal records of sows were used to derive daily population-at-risk and mortality for each municipality. Temperature–mortality associations were assessed using a distributed lag nonlinear model (DLNM) within a conditional quasi-Poisson regression framework, adjusting for humidity through natural splines.

Result

Across 34,008 farm–day observations, mean daily mortality ranged from 0.144 to 0.353 deaths per 1,000 sow-days, with substantial day-to-day variability across municipalities. The highest maximum daily value was observed in Seros (60.468 deaths per 1,000 sow-days). Mean daily temperature ranged from 10.47 °C to 16.89 °C, while the full observed temperature range across municipalities extended from -8.15 °C to 34.49 °C. Mean relative humidity ranged from 59% to 67%, with observed daily values between 10% and 98%. The distributed lag non-linear model showed a J-shaped cumulative temperature–mortality association over lags

0–21 days. The minimum mortality temperature (MMT) was 15.4 °C. Below the MMT, cumulative relative risk increased only modestly, reaching approximately 1.1–1.2 around 5–7 °C, although uncertainty widened substantially at the lower end of the temperature distribution. Above the MMT, the increase in cumulative risk was steeper, with cumulative RR approaching 2.5 (95%CI) at the highest observed temperatures. Lag–response analyses indicated that most temperature effects occurred within 0–3 days. Overall, 14.19% of deaths were attributable to temperature ($\approx 3,658$ deaths), with heat accounting for 10.76% and cold 3.4%.

Discussion

Physiologically, heat stress triggers peripheral vasodilation, splanchnic blood flow redistribution, acute cardiac failure, and intestinal barrier disruption leading to endotoxemia and systemic inflammation, collectively explaining the observed short-lag mortality pattern^{1–3}. Compared with ruminants, monogastric species have received considerably less attention regarding climate-related impacts. Importantly, indoor housing should not be assumed protective, as pigs possess few functional sweat glands and rely primarily on respiratory evaporative cooling, rendering them acutely sensitive to high temperatures even in conventionally ventilated facilities where inlet air cooling is absent. The identified MMT falls within the range generally considered compatible with sow thermal comfort^{2,4}, which helps explain the modest cold-related risk and the steeper mortality increase above MMT. As extreme heat events become more frequent and intense in Europe, elevated nighttime temperatures during heat waves may further limit physiological recovery and amplify this acute mortality risk.

Facing this fact, adaptation strategies should prioritize resilience to short-duration, high-intensity thermal exposure. Rapidly acting cooling technologies—such as evaporative cooling pads and high-pressure fogging systems—are most effective within the critical 0–2 day risk window and should be complemented by improved ventilation and building insulation to buffer future climate-driven mortality risk in intensive swine production systems.

Conclusion

This study identified a minimum mortality temperature of 15.4 °C and a J-shaped temperature–mortality relationship in breeding sows, with heat exposure causing acute increases in mortality within 0–2 days and cold having weaker, less certain effects. Overall, 14.19% of sow deaths were attributable to ambient temperature, highlighting a substantial burden for production and welfare. As climate change drives more frequent and intense heat events in Europe (specially in southern countries), the main threat to sow survival arises from short, extreme temperature spikes rather than gradual warming. These results underscore the need for rapid cooling measures, supported by adequate ventilation and housing design, to reduce acute heat-related mortality and protect sow welfare under intensifying climate extremes.

Reference

1. Mikovits C, Zollitsch W, Hörtenhuber SJ, et al. Impacts of global warming on confined livestock systems for growing-fattening pigs: simulation of heat stress for 1981 to 2017 in Central Europe. *Int J Biometeorol.* 2019;63(2):221–230. doi:10.1007/s00484-018-01655-0

2. Renaudeau D, Dourmad JY. Review: Future consequences of climate change for European Union pig production. *animal*. 2022;16:100372. doi:10.1016/j.animal.2021.100372
3. Vitt R, Weber L, Zollitsch W, et al. Modelled performance of energy saving airtreatment devices to mitigate heat stress for confined livestock buildings in Central Europe. *Biosystems Engineering*. 2017;164:85-97. doi:10.1016/j.biosystemseng.2017.09.013
4. Cecil MR, Neeno SM, Byrd MH, et al. Determining the optimal macroenvironment temperature to house lactating sows and their litters. *J Anim Sci*. 2025;103:skaf255. doi:10.1093/jas/skaf255

Evaluating production and transport factors of transit loss in market hogs and predicting loads with losses using machine learning

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Introduction

Loading and transporting pigs from farms to abattoirs is the final step in realizing economic value. Transit loss (TL) of market weight pigs is defined as pigs that die or become non-ambulatory (NA), meaning they are unable to

walk or move on their own, during loading and transport from the farm to the abattoir, causing both economic losses and animal welfare concerns. Site-level factors, such as barn type and health status, and truck-level factors, such as loading density, traveling distance and seasons¹, were reported in the previous studies. Because these losses arise from multiple interacting factors and related data are often fragmented, identifying their causes is challenging. This study aimed to analyze combined impact of different-level factors on TL and use machine-learning methods to predict the risk of TL.

Methods

We analyzed 30,291 transport records (each corresponding to a truckload of pigs) from 1,928 finishing batches across 348 sites in the Midwest USA between January 2022 and May 2025. R scripts integrated finishing closeouts, transport summaries, and loss outcomes. A negative binomial mixed-effects model was built with manual stepwise selection to estimate the per-load TL ratio and compared it across variable categories. An XGBoost model with an 80:20 split was applied to classify loads with high or low TL and generated a truck score by scaling the negative predictive value from 0 to 10.

Results

The average TL per load was 1.08% (95% CI: 1.07–1.11). Of the 33 initial variables, 15 entered the final model. Sites using wet-dry feeders, batches with lighter pigs upon arrival, without PRRSV vaccination, or with higher average daily feed intake (ADFI) associated with higher TL risk. TL was also more likely for loads transported in fall or winter, with short distance, and later cuts. At the truck level, heavier individuals and entire truck, and uneven weight distributions increased TL

probability. 36 variables were used in the machine learning model. The XGBoost model achieved 82.38% accuracy (95% CI: 81.39%-83.33%; sensitivity: 83.92%; specificity: 80.85%), and its 0–10 truck score decreased with risk, showing a -0.682 correlation (Pearson) with TL.

Discussion

Our results provide practical guidance for reducing TL in swine production. Pigs under greater health or stress challenges are more likely to experience TL. In this study, lack of PRRSV vaccination was associated with higher health risk and increased TL. Lower body weight at entry and higher ADFI may increase digestive and growth stress. Feed and water delivery systems also influence ADFI; mixed wet–dry feeders may accelerate intake, potentially increasing growth stress and TL risk.

Contrary to the common perception that heat stress drives losses², colder seasons posed greater risk in this study. Since the production were from Midwest U.S.A., the summer is milder while the winter is seriously cold. The animals may suffer more from diseases than heat stress. Also under the cold, pigs are more likely to be close to each other, causing them to crush into each, leading to NA in pigs. For longer transport distance, pigs are likely to lie down, reduce the chance of crushing, which explains the short transport have higher TL.

Trucks with heavier pigs and imbalanced weighted pigs were more likely to get higher TL rate. Heavier pigs are more susceptible to stress and physical strain during handling and transport due to reduced thermoregulation and limited mobility, which can increase the likelihood of non-ambulatory events³. Imbalanced load composition may further intensify space competition and instability.

Loads transported near the group-close date were likely at higher risk because pigs had grown excessively heavy by that time or because animals in poorer condition were intentionally left for later shipments to allow additional recovery before marketing. As for machine learning, it provides a probability of pre-assessment of TL for truckloads by providing the load-risk score.

Conclusion

Pigs under higher health risk or experiencing lower growth performance exhibit a greater risk of TL. Cold seasons are found to be riskier in this study. Adjusting transport timing and balancing load composition can reduce losses and improve animal welfare. Regarding machine learning, it offers a probability-based pre-assessment of TL for truckloads by assigning a load-risk score.

References

1. Aradom Messmer S, Gebresenbet G, Bulitta SF, Bobobee E, Adam M. Effect of transport times on welfare of pigs. *Journal of agricultural science and technology A*. 2012;2(4A).
2. Zurbrigg K, Dreumel T, Rothschild M, Alves D, Friendship R, O'Sullivan T. Pig-level risk factors for in-transit losses in swine: A review. *Canadian Journal of Animal Science*. 2017;97. doi:10.1139/CJAS-2016-0193
3. Aradom Messmer S, Gebresenbet G, Bulitta SF, Bobobee E, Adam M. Effect of transport times on welfare of pigs. *Journal of agricultural science and technology A*. 2012;2(4A).

Improving boar freezing extenders: use of seminal extracellular vesicles from AI doses.

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Introduction

In swine production, artificial insemination (AI) is performed with liquid semen stored between 15–18 °C. However, for long-term preservation, sperm cryopreservation in liquid nitrogen is required (De Andrade et al., 2022). During freezing, sperm cells are exposed to cryoprotectants and cooled to -196 °C, where cryodamage arises from ice crystal formation, temperature stress, osmotic imbalance, and oxidative stress, impairing membrane integrity and function (Álvarez-Rodríguez et al., 2024).

Seminal extracellular vesicles (sEVs), present in seminal plasma, play a key role in intercellular communication and may protect sperm from oxidative damage (Martín-San Juan et al., 2026), acting as potential cryoprotectants. This study aimed to evaluate the effect of adding sEVs to freezing extenders to improve boar sperm cryopreservation.

Methods

sEVs were enriched from pooled diluted seminal plasma from six AI doses of high-fertility boars. Seminal plasma was sequentially centrifuged and concentrated. sEVs were purified by SEC columns (IZON)

and re-concentrated to obtain enriched EVs ($1.3 \times 10^{11} \pm 4.9 \times 10^9$ EVs/mL) diluted in BTS. For cryopreservation, 48 AI doses were assigned to four treatments: i) control (CTL), without sEVs supplementation; ii) 1X_sEVs (6.5×10^9 EVs/mL); iii) 3X_sEVs (1.95×10^{10} EVs/mL); and iv) 6X_sEVs (3.9×10^{10} EVs/mL), added to the cooling extender (LEY). Sperm samples ($\sim 300 \times 10^6$ spermatozoa pooled from 4 AI doses) were centrifuged ($1500 \times g$, 5 min), diluted (1:1) in LEY with treatments, and cooled from 15 °C to 5 °C, 2 h. Samples were resuspended in freezing extender (LEYGO), and frozen in 0.5 mL straws using a controlled-rate protocol. Thawing was performed at 37 °C for 20 s, followed by dilution (1:1) in BTS. Motility (total motility (TM, %), progressive motility (PM, %), curvilinear velocity (VCL, $\mu\text{m/s}$), and straight-line velocity (VSL, $\mu\text{m/s}$)), viability and acrosome integrity (PI/PNA-FITC), and oxidative stress (YO-PRO-1/DHE) were evaluated at fresh, cooled, and thawed stages.

Results

After cooling, 6X_sEVs treatment reduced the percentage of live sperm with intact acrosome (PI-/PNA-), similarly to 1X_sEVs, while also decreasing dead sperm with reacted acrosome (PI+/PNA+) and increasing dead sperm with intact acrosome (PI+/PNA-). It also increased PM compared to CTL and reduced VCL compared to fresh samples, whereas other treatments showed no motility differences. The percentage of live non-oxidized sperm (YO-PRO-1-/DHE-) decreased in 1X_sEVs and 3X_sEVs, along with dead oxidized sperm (YO-PRO-1+/DHE+). Conversely, 6X_sEVs reduced dead non-oxidized sperm (YO-PRO-1+/DHE-). During freezing, VCL decreased in all treatments, while VSL decreased in 3X_sEVs and 6X_sEVs, and TM decreased in 6X_sEVs,

with no changes in PM. The 3X_sEVs treatment improved viability (IP-/PNA-), and reduced dead with reacted acrosome (PI+/PNA-) with 1X_sEVs, while 6X_sEVs increased PI+/PNA+. No differences in oxidation were observed.

Discussion

Although the protective effect of sEVs in boar sperm cells has been described (Martín-San Juan et al., 2026; Sullivan & Saez, 2013), their potential role during cooling and freezing remains unknown. The use of sEVs during cooling reduced velocity but increased PM, while some treatments decreased the proportion of live, non-reacted, and oxidized spermatozoa, suggesting a potentially negative effect on sperm quality. This contradictory response may be explained by a loss of interaction between sEVs and sperm membranes during cooling. Cold shock induces lipid phase transitions that could disrupt membrane structure and fluidity (Jäkel et al., 2021). Moreover, sEVs contain high levels of cholesterol, which stabilize membranes (Drobnis et al., 1993). Cold shock may affect both spermatozoa and sEVs, altering membrane fluidity and impairing their interaction. Similarly, freezing reduced motility and viability at higher sEVs concentrations, suggesting that excessive sEVs interaction or vesicle damage, possibly due to ice crystal formation, may compromise sperm quality after thawing (Susa et al., 2023).

Conclusion

The addition of sEVs to the LEY extender did not improve boar sperm cryosurvival and may impair sperm quality, particularly at higher concentrations, probably due to altered membrane fluidity and disrupted sperm-sEVs interactions, highlighting the need for further

mechanistic studies to optimize conditions before its practical implementation.

References

1. Álvarez-Rodríguez, M., et al. (2024). *Animals*, 14(6), 914. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ani14060914>
2. De Andrade, A., et al. (2022). *Animal Reproduction Science*, 236, 106906. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anireprosci.2021.106906>
3. Drobnis, E., et al. (1993). *The Journal of Experimental Zoology*, 265(4), 432–437. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jez.1402650413>
4. Jäkel, H., et al. (2021). *Cytometry. Part A: The Journal of the International Society for Analytical Cytology*, 99(10), 1033–1041. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cyto.a.24301>
5. Martín-San Juan, A., et al. (2026). (p. 2026.03.16.712050). <https://doi.org/10.64898/2026.03.16.712050>
6. Sullivan, R., & Saez, F. (2013). *Reproduction*, 146(1), R21-35. <https://doi.org/10.1530/REP-13-0058>
7. Susa, F., et al. (2023). *ACS Biomaterials Science & Engineering*, 9(10), 5871–5885. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsbomaterials.3c00678>

From Cell Model to Animal Trial: Evaluating the Role of Butyric Acid in Controlling Intestinal Inflammation in Piglets

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Introduction

Butyric acid (BA) is a short-chain fatty acid naturally produced in the gastrointestinal tract of animals through microbial fermentation. Its supplementation, particularly in protected forms, has emerged as a safe and effective alternative to antibiotic growth promoters (AGPs) in young animal nutrition. BA is known to exert beneficial effects on intestinal morphology, including enhanced villus development, modulation of gut microbiota, and improved nutrient digestibility. Moreover, recent evidence suggests that BA plays a key role in regulating inflammatory responses in the small intestine, thereby contributing to improved gut health, especially in post-weaning piglets raised under antibiotic-free conditions. The present study aimed to investigate the anti-inflammatory potential of BA using both *in vitro* and *in vivo* approaches.

Material and Methods

In vitro, the porcine intestinal epithelial cell line IPEC-J2 was employed as a model to simulate enterocyte responses. Inflammation was induced using lipopolysaccharide (LPS), and cells were pre-treated with increasing

concentrations of BA (4 to 200 µg/mL) at 37 °C for 1 hour, followed by co-incubation with LPS (10 ng/mL) for an additional hour. The expression levels of pro-inflammatory cytokine genes were subsequently quantified. *In vivo*, a total of 1,600 piglets weaned at 21 days of age were allocated into two experimental groups across 32 pens. The control group received a standard diet without supplementation, while the treatment group was fed a diet supplemented with a protected form of BA (Butirex C4®) at 3 kg/t from day 21 to 35, and 2 kg/t from day 35 to 63. Growth performance parameters were recorded biweekly at the pen level, and faecal consistency was assessed daily to monitor diarrhoea incidence.

Results

In the *in vitro* model, LPS stimulation significantly upregulated mRNA expression levels of key inflammatory cytokines, including IL-8, TNF-α, and CCL20 (12-, 54-, and 137-fold increases, respectively; $P < 0.001$). Pre-treatment with BA markedly attenuated this inflammatory response, leading to a significant dose-dependent reduction in cytokine gene expression compared to LPS-treated cells (reductions ranging from 4- to 17-fold; $P < 0.001$).

In the *in vivo* trial, piglets receiving BA supplementation demonstrated significant improvements in growth performance between 21 and 63 days of age, including increased average daily gain (ADG; +4.2%) and improved feed conversion ratio (FCR; -3.4%) compared to the control group ($P < 0.05$). Additionally, the incidence of diarrhoea was significantly reduced in the BA-supplemented group (-26.2%; $P < 0.05$), indicating enhanced gut health and resilience.

Conclusions

Overall, the findings from this study demonstrate that BA exerts direct anti-inflammatory effects on intestinal epithelial cells, which are consistent with the observed improvements in growth performance and health status in post-weaning piglets. The combined in vitro and in vivo approach highlights the potential of BA as a sustainable nutritional strategy and supports the use of cell-based models as valuable tools for the preliminary evaluation of functional feed additives prior to animal trials.

Association between sow body condition caliper measurements and sow reproductive performance across three parities

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Introduction

Reproductive performance is a key determinant of sow productivity and is influenced by multiple biological and management factors. Body condition is one of these factors and has been associated with reproductive performance in sows (Ajay et al., 2023). The sow body condition caliper (SBC) provides a practical and objective method to assess body condition under commercial conditions. Previous studies have reported associations between SBC measurements and

reproductive traits such as number born alive, number weaned and piglet survival (Authement and Knauer, 2023). However, these relationships have primarily been evaluated in multiparous sows without considering changes across successive parities within the same individuals. Therefore, the objectives of this study were to 1) investigate the association between reproductive performance and SBC across three parities; 2) evaluate the relationship between number of piglets weaned (NPW) and SBC in dynamics during the first lactation; and 3) assess the association between SBC at weaning in parity 1 and subsequent reproductive performance.

Materials and Methods

Data from 1,424 PIC Camborough® sows with complete records from parity (P) 1 to P3 were obtained from a Spanish commercial farm. For each parity, information on total piglets born (TB), born alive (BA), percentage BA, and NPW was available. Additionally, sow body condition was assessed using SBC at pre-farrowing and at weaning. SBC change and percentage change during lactation were calculated. All analyses were conducted in R (v4.4.0). Associations between SBC and reproductive performance were evaluated using linear mixed models including parity, season, and their interaction as fixed effects, with sow included as a random effect. Associations between NPW and SBC dynamics during the first lactation were analysed using linear regression models, including NPW as a continuous predictor. The relationship between SBC at weaning in parity 1 and subsequent (re)productive performance was evaluated using linear regression models, with SBC included as continuous predictor.

Results and discussion

TB, BA and NPW increased as parity progressed ($P < 0.001$). SBC at weaning differed across parities ($P < 0.01$), although differences were small (P1: 13.69; P2: +0.02; P3: -0.13). SBC change during lactation was greater in P1 (-0.94) compared with later parities ($P < 0.05$; P2: +0.05, P3: +0.17 vs P1), but when expressed as percentage change, no differences between parities were observed ($P > 0.05$), which is consistent with previous reports of greater body reserve mobilisation in primiparous sows, although the magnitude of these differences was small. In P1, NPW was negatively associated with SBC at weaning (-0.16 ± 0.03) and with greater SBC loss during lactation (-0.17 ± 0.03 ; $P < 0.001$) which is consistent with the increased metabolic demands associated with larger litters (Authement and Knauer, 2023) SBC at weaning in P1 was positively associated with SBC at farrowing in P2 (0.56 ± 0.02) and P3 (0.46 ± 0.03 , $P < 0.001$), and with TB in P2 (0.18 ± 0.06) and P3 (0.10 ± 0.05 ; $P < 0.05$), indicating that sows with greater SBC at the end of P1 tend to maintain better body condition in subsequent parities, highlighting the importance of effective management during lactation to preserve body condition, whereas associations with reproductive performance were small, likely reflecting the multifactorial nature of this trait.

Conclusions

Under the conditions of this study, associations between caliper measurements and reproductive performance, within and across parities, were small in magnitude and likely of limited biological relevance, reflecting the multifactorial nature of reproductive performance. The relatively homogeneous nature of the study population may have also contributed to the limited variability observed.

Nonetheless, body condition remains a key component of sow productivity, highlighting the importance of effective management during lactation to minimise body condition losses and avoid compromising subsequent reproductive performance.

References

1. Ajay, A., et al. 2023. *Tropical animal health and production*, 55(6), p.393.
- Authement, M.R. et al. 2023. *Open J. Anim. Sci*, 13(3), pp.310-322.

Optimization of post-cervical insemination in gilts with Monzal®

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Introduction

Post-cervical artificial insemination (PCAI) in gilts presents important technical limitations, mainly due to the difficulty of passing the catheter through the cervix, which reduces the applicability of this technique under commercial conditions. Strategies aimed at improving cervical relaxation and facilitating probe passage may enhance the efficiency of PCAI and its adoption in gilt management. The aim of this study was to evaluate the effect of Monzal® administration on cervical probe acceptance, fertility, and prolificacy in gilts.

Materials and methods

The trial was conducted on a commercial farm and included a total of 154 gilts synchronized using altrenogest and gonadotropins. Animals were divided into two groups: a control group

inseminated using the conventional cervical technique and a treatment group subjected to PCAI. In cases where the catheter did not successfully pass through the cervix, Monzal® was administered, and the procedure was repeated after 10 minutes. If passage was still unsuccessful, cervical insemination was performed.

Results

The administration of Monzal® significantly increased the success rate of probe passage from 51% to 65%, representing a 25% improvement in the number of PCAI procedures performed. This positive effect was consistent regardless of service number, day of estrus, or body condition. No detrimental effects on fertility were observed. On the contrary, the treatment group showed a 12.8% increase in fertility at ultrasound ($p=0.04$). Additionally, an increase of 0.6 total piglets born per litter was recorded in the Monzal® group compared to the control group.

Conclusion

In conclusion, Monzal® is an effective tool to facilitate PCAI in gilts, improving catheter passage without compromising reproductive performance. Its use contributes to enhanced prolificacy and represents a practical strategy to optimize reproductive management and production efficiency on commercial pig farms.

Timing matters: modelling the interplay among maternally derived antibodies, prevalence of infection and PCV2 vaccination in swine

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Introduction and Objectives

Porcine circovirus 2 (PCV2) remains one of the most impactful endemic pathogens in global swine production. Although piglet vaccination is widely implemented, its effectiveness is influenced by maternally derived antibodies (MDA) and the timing of natural infection. This study aimed to develop a model to explore how MDA levels and infection pressure shape PCV2 transmission dynamics and to identify optimal vaccination timing under different epidemiological contexts.

Materials and Methods

A stochastic individual-based model was developed using the EMULSION framework to simulate a single batch production in a farrow-

to-finish production system. The model integrates horizontal transmission, age-dependent MDA decay, vaccine-induced humoral immunity, and clinical outcomes, including PCV2 subclinical infection (PCV2-SI), systemic disease (PCV2-SD), and their consequences on growth performance.

Four MDA distributions at weaning (low, medium, high and very high, which are <0.5, 0.5-1.0, 1.0-2.0 and >2.0, respectively, with PCV2 Ingezim Circovirus IgG ELISA test) and three PCV2 prevalence levels at nursery entry (1, 5 and 10%) were combined with six intervention strategies: no vaccination (NV) and vaccination at 14, 21, 28, 35, or 42 days of age. 72 epidemiological scenarios were simulated (10 replicates each). Model parameterization was based on published literature. Outputs included PCV2-SI and PCV2-SD prevalence, viraemia dynamics, growth performance and economic indicators. Model robustness was supported by two-phase sensitivity analysis (one-at-a-time screening and full factorial design).

Results and Discussion

Under NV conditions, higher MDA levels delayed PCV2 infection onset, whereas higher PCV2 prevalence at weaning accelerated viral circulation. Vaccination performance was MDA-dependent. In farms with low to high MDA levels, early vaccination (14-21 days of age) minimized PCV2-SI and maximized growth, reducing PCV2-SI and PCV2-SD by up to 94% and 97%, respectively. In contrast, very high MDA levels required delayed vaccination (28–42 days of age) to avoid immune interference. NV pigs showed 5 kg lower finishing BW, while optimal vaccination increased economic margin by 0.05–0.10 €/kg live weight.

Conclusion

This modelling approach provides a robust framework to support data-driven optimization of PCV2 vaccination timing. Integrating serological (MDA) and virological (PCV2 prevalence at weaning) information enables tailored vaccination strategies adapted to farm-specific epidemiological conditions.

Keywords: Maternal derived antibodies, PCV2, Stochastic modelling, Vaccination timing

Identification of key enteric pathogens in swine diarrhoea across different production stages

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Introduction

Porcine enteric disorders remain a major concern for efficient and sustainable swine production, particularly in the context of under reduced antibiotic use and the withdrawal of zinc oxide. In fact, diarrhoea is one of the main causes of mortality, particularly during early life stages, and it is associated with reduced growth, with direct consequences for herd productivity (Sjölund et al., 2014). This mortality, which mainly occurs during the lactation and nursery phases, reduces the number of female animals available for gilt replacement. Moreover, health challenges during later development (corresponding to the growing–finishing period), can compromise longevity and reproductive

performance in future sows (Patterson & Foxcroft, 2019). Thus, identifying the main pathogens involved in enteric disorders across production stages is essential for improving piglet survival, optimising sow herd performance and replacement quality, and supporting the development of targeted, stage-specific control and prevention strategies.

Materials & Methods

A total of 450 rectal swabs were collected from ten breeding herds, with documented history of diarrhoeal outbreaks, and their corresponding nursery and fattening units between October 2024 and May 2025. From each farm, 15 individual samples were obtained and analysed for major enteric pathogens by PCR in pools of five samples. Pathogen detection prevalence was calculated as the proportion of positive pools within each production phase, and co-detections were recorded. Significant differences were set at $p < 0.05$.

Results & Discussion

In lactation, *E. coli* was detected in all pools (100%), which is expected given its role as a common member of the intestinal microbiota. Toxinotyping revealed that EAST1 was present in all samples (100%), followed by eae (86.6%). The STb toxin was also frequent (70%), as well as F41 (60%), indicating the presence of enterotoxigenic and enteropathogenic *E. coli*, the main pathotypes involved in neonatal diarrhoea. *Clostridium perfringens* was identified in 80% of pools; among the virulence factors assessed, α -toxin was detected in 80% and β 2 in 73.3%, while β toxin was not detected. The presence of these toxins does not necessarily confirm pathogenic involvement, as they are common in commensal type A strains, although β 2 has

been associated with severe clinical cases. *Clostridioides difficile* was present in 43.3% of pools, suggesting a contributory role. Rotavirus A and C were detected in 40% of pools, often in co-infections associated with increased clinical severity. The relevance of these findings lies not only in piglet mortality, but in the impact on early growth and uniformity, both of which directly influence the quality and availability of future replacement gilts. This has practical implications, as control strategies focused on a single agent are unlikely to be sufficient. Instead, interventions targeting sow immunity, colostrum quality, and early microbial exposure become critical to reduce pathogen pressure in this stage.

In the nursery phase, *E. coli* remained predominant (100%), with F18 detected in 73.3%, a feature common in pathogenic post-weaning strains. Detection of Stx2e in 20% of pools indicates circulation of verotoxigenic *E. coli*, relevant for oedema disease and of particular importance in replacement gilts due to high associated mortality. Porcine epidemic diarrhoea virus (PEDV, 20%) was also identified, a pathogen that typically causes outbreaks with high mortality, highlighting the importance of strict biosecurity measures.

In the fattening phase, number of pathogen detection was lower than earlier stages. Particularly, three pathogens were detected: PEDV (20%), *Cryptosporidium* spp. (10%), and *Lawsonia intracellularis* (10%). The high proportion of negative pools supports a multifactorial origin of the observed diarrhea, with the contribution of non-infectious factors such as diet, environment, and management.

Conclusions

This study shows that the highest positivity to different pathogens was detected at lactation phase, where co-detections were frequent,

being the most detected pathogens *E. coli*, *C. perfringens* type A, *C. difficile*, and rotaviruses. These findings highlight the relevance of early-life stages in the development of enteric disease and support the need to focus control measures at this stage, particularly through sow-based strategies aimed at reducing diarrhoea in suckling and recently weaned piglets. Furthermore, these results emphasise the value of routine pathogen monitoring across production stages to inform targeted interventions, reduce early-life health challenges, and ultimately improve the robustness and uniformity of replacement gilts.

References

1. Patterson, J., & Foxcroft, G. (2019). Gilt management for fertility and longevity. *Animals*, 9(7), 434. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ani9070434>
2. Sjölund, M., Zoric, M., y Wallgren, P. (2014, May 7–9). Financial impact of disease on pig production. Part III: Gastrointestinal disorders. 6th European Symposium of Porcine Health Management, Sorrento, Italia.

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